

Ride 2Rail

D5.1 PERFORMANCE TARGETS AND KPIS

This project has received funding from the Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 881825

Project Acronym	Ride2Rail
Starting date	01/12/2019
Duration (in months)	36
Deliverable number	D5.1
Call Identifier	S2R-OC-IP4-01-2019
GRANT Agreement no	881825
Due date of the Deliverable	30/11/2021
Actual re-submission date	30/03/2022
Responsible/Author	UNEW
Dissemination level	PU
Work package	WP5
Main editor	David Golightly
Reviewer(s)	FIT, CERTH
Status of document (draft/issued)	ISSUED

Reviewed: yes

Consortium of partners

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DOCUMENT HISTORY		
Revision	Date	Description
0.1	07/12/20210	Draft submitted to contributors for comments
1.0	20/12/2021	Final version submitted to consortium
2.0	29/03/2022	Revised in response to reviewers' comments

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of this deliverable is to specify the methodology required to monitor the KPIs as defined in D4.2. The objectives of this methodology are to be valid and reliable in terms of how data is captured and measured, while being suitable for the constraints of demonstration sites and, in a later phase, any dissemination locations. Additionally, the methodology has been designed to minimise effort on the part of demo participants in order to encourage their accurate reporting of the usage of Ride2Rail, and to conform to the technical constraints of both the Ride2Rail technical delivery, and the Shift2Rail Travel Companion.

The process has been applied in the following way. The potential channels for capturing data have been explored in depth – these include monitoring of Ride2Rail usage and behaviours directly from the Ride2Rail ecosystem, including the wider Shift2Rail Call For Members (CFM) ecosystem, and from asking the demo participants directly (e.g. through a survey). This analysis was conducted for each of the KPIs to identify the benefits and limitations of different approaches.

The overall conclusion of the approach has been to use an approach that combines

1) an online survey that will collect key data about the use of the Ride2Rail service, and basic demographic information. This will also serve as a platform for the usability approach (see D5.2).

2) data collected directly from the Ride2Rail ecosystem. This will give additional validation of the data generated by the survey, as well as information about number of users.

All data is anonymised in compliance with GDPR. The deliverable also highlights a small number of open questions that must be resolved for successful monitoring.

Abbreviations and acronyms

CFM	Call For Members
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
IT	Information Technology
IP	Innovation Programme
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
R2R	Ride2Rail
T	Task
TC	Travel Companion
WP	Work Package

2. BACKGROUND

2.1. Shift2Rail context

Shift2Rail is the first European rail initiative to seek focused research and innovation and market-driven solutions by accelerating the integration of new and advanced technologies into innovative rail product solutions. Shift2Rail promotes the competitiveness of the European rail industry and meets changing EU transport needs. Research carried out under this Horizon 2020 initiative develops the necessary technology to complete the Single European Railway Area.

The delivery of Shift2Rail is based around five Innovation Programmes (IPs); the focus of this deliverable is IP4 – ‘IT solutions for attractive rail services’. To become a more attractive option, rail must respond to customer needs to support anytime, anywhere, door-to-door, intermodal journeys encompassing distinct modes of transportation. Rail must achieve interoperability with other transport modes and mobility services, with regions, cities and people engaged in social and economic activities, and with the key elements of the supply chains which can make rail products and services available to those people. In order to achieve this, rail needs to take due advantage of the increasing connectivity of people and objects, the availability of European Global Navigation Satellite System-based locations, the advances in cloud computing, big, linked and open data and the propagation of internet and social media. The step towards sharing data needs to be considered and progressively developed, in order to enable service developers to provide connected travellers with the services they need and expect.

2.2. Ride2Rail

A key aspect of delivering more attractive services is by delivering end-to-end (or first- and last-mile) travel services that enable rail as their core mode of mobility. This can be challenging in a rural environment, where connectivity to rail is problematic. It is also relevant in urban or peri-urban environments where there may be poorer provision of public transit or congestion of roads.

Contributing to Shift2Rail’s IP4, Ride2Rail’s overall objective is to develop an innovative framework for intelligent mobility, facilitating the efficient combination of flexible (ride-sharing) and scheduled transport services (rail, bus, and other public transport services), thus enhancing the performance of the overall mobility system. Ride2Rail should, in particular, address the first and last mile problem by offering a wider range of transit options, while harnessing the capacity of single occupancy vehicles, along with existing, or future, demand responsive transit.

Ride2Rail aims to integrate multiple (public/private/social) data sets and existing transport platforms for promoting an effective ride sharing practice of citizens, making it a complementary transport mode that extends public transport networks.

The objectives of the Ride2Rail project are:

- To develop an innovative framework for intelligent mobility, facilitating efficient combination of flexible and scheduled transport services, integrating real-time information about public transport and ride sharing;
- To facilitate the comparison and the choice between multiple options/services classified by a set of criteria, for example environmental, travel time, comfort, cost;
- To encourage carpooling (and ride sharing acceptance) to complement public transport;
- To enhance the performance of the overall mobility system, reducing road congestion and environmental impact, reinforcing the mobility offer in rural and low-demand areas;
- To combine travel offer classifications and software components, integrating them into existing collective and on-demand transport services;
- To induct the access to high-capacity services thanks to easy-to-use multimodal and integrated travel planning, booking, ticketing and payment features;
- To design, develop and test in four real demonstrators a set of software components for the IP4 ecosystem, including an enhanced Travel Companion and the crowd-based Transport Service Provider;
- To produce recommendations for replicability.

2.3. Work Package 5 context

The project will implement demonstrations of the Ride2Rail service in four locations – Padua, Italy; Athens, Greece; Brno, Czech Republic; Helsinki, Finland. A critical aspect of these demonstrations is to understand their performance against the aims of the project, and in terms of supporting sustainability actions in these locations.

Workpackage 5 of Ride2Rail sets out the evaluation activities for Ride2Rail. Specifically, it draws upon the definition of KPIs (defined in Workpackage 4) and uses these as evaluation targets. Figure 1 illustrates the flow of tasks in WP5. T5.1 specifies the nature of KPI measurement by understanding the feasibility of different measurement techniques. T5.3 will actively measure the KPIs during demo execution in WP4. Ultimately, the KPIs will be used to inform the impact analysis for Ride2Rail (as calculated in T5.4). These impact areas are:

1. increase the number of multi-occupancy vehicle trips, as opposed to single occupancy-vehicle trips;
2. increase access to public transit for users in a rural and/or suburban setting;
3. contribute to minimising emissions.

In parallel, T5.2 sets out usability assessment criteria for Ride2Rail, described in Deliverable D5.2.

Figure 1 Task Flow for WP5

3. OBJECTIVES AND SCOPE

3.1. Deliverable objectives

The aim of this deliverable is describe the KPI measurement approach to be applied to the demos (WP4) and therefore underpin evaluation and impact assessment (Tasks 5.3 and 5.4).

In order to meet this aim, a number of objectives are covered:

- Scoping the work including restating the KPIS;
- Identifying the potential options for KPI measurement;
- Describing the approach used to assess the feasibility of options;
- Presenting the outcome of feasibility assessment;
- Describing the final methodology.

3.2. Scope

Scope and assumptions are as follows:

- The measurement approach is applied to the generic KPIS as described in D4.2. Local measures are not covered by this document, though the mechanisms described can be used to support local measures.
- The monitoring period will be the duration of the demos in each of the four sites.
- All KPI targets and measurement methods are based on both technical assumptions and demo site operational conditions as of M24.
- While the KPI measurement approaches are generic, it is necessary to differentiate between demo sites so as to interpret data in terms of each demo sites KPI target.
- The methodology needs to confirm to GDPR generally, and specifically with the data plan specified in D1.3.

3.3. Inputs and outputs

3.3.1. Inputs

- WP3 provides the technical functions and integration that will be evaluated in WP5. Therefore, the measurement approach for T5.1 must reflect these technical capabilities. Specifically, WP3 has identified a number of technical constraints in terms of the ecosystem of Ride2Rail / Shift2Rail, that influence the feasibility of data collection.
- WP4 provides the demo context where Ride2Rail will be evaluated. This covers both the contextual factors (such as the types of trips likely to be encountered in a demo area) as well as the capacity for demo site leaders to support evaluation activities, which influences the feasibility of evaluation.
- D4.2 has provided the definition of the KPIS that any measurement methodology needs to address.

3.3.2. Outputs

- The direct output of T5.1 is T5.3 which will actually record the evaluation measures. Subsequently, T5.4 will use those measures to make impact evaluation.
- The platform selected in T5.1 also sets out measurement capabilities that could potentially be used by T5.2 to deliver usability evaluation measures.

- Work in D5.1 has been conducted in parallel with D4.3 Monitoring Tools.

4. APPROACH

D4.2 defined a number of KPIS applicable across the Ride2Rail evaluation. These KPIS are presented in Table 1 (NB while this table uses the term “Ride2Rail App”, the elicitation process presented in Section 4 highlights there is not a single app, but instead a suite of extended “R2R” functions as part of the Shift2Rail “enhanced” Travel Companion and a Ride2Rail Driver Companion app – see Section 5.4 for more details).

Table 1 KPI list (from D4.2)

KPI	DEFINITION
KPI#1 Number of Ride2Rail app users	Demo site users who download the app and request at least one trip
KPI#2 Number of completed Ride2Rail app trips	A completed trip made by a demo site app user
KPI#3 Number of completed multi-occupancy vehicle trips with R2R app	A completed trip made by a demo site app user that involves either rideshare OR Robobus (Helsinki)
KPI#4 Number of completed trips involving public transit/rail with R2R app	A completed multi-modal trip
KPI#5 Number of completed commuter trips with R2R app	A completed trip that is a regular journey (work or education) conducted 4 (including outward or return) or more times a week
KPI#6 Number of completed rural trips with R2R app	A complete trip where origin or/and destination is from/to a rural (or suburban) location
KPI#7 Number of Ride2Rail app downloads	Number of times the app has been downloaded by unique users

There are a number of technical constraints on the Ride2Rail ecosystem that impact the monitoring of these KPIS. While some of these limit the feasibility of certain measurement methods (e.g. limits on data availability within Ride2Rail to identify completed trips) other constraints may be useful (e.g. the need to manually install the app means it is easier to identify participating users).

Similarly, the needs of demo sites in some cases constrain the measurement approaches (e.g. limited capacity to send physical surveys to users) but equally may be useful (e.g. demo participation incentives should only be received after completion of the survey).

In order to define a measurement methodology that reflects these constraints and opportunities, an approach was selected that identifies the most appropriate methods. This approach used the following method:

- Step 1: Determine criteria for successful measurement methodology;
- Step 2: Identify potential measurement approaches;

- Step 3: Use a KPI table to elicit feedback from WP3 and WP4 representatives on the appropriateness of potential measurement approaches, in general and for each specific KPI. This also involved clarification from CFM;
 - Step 4: Determine specific KPI measurement methods;
 - Step 5: Identify a single, simplified approach that covers multiple KPIs – this is in order to streamline KPI measurement for demo site partners, for participant and for analysis in T5.3 / T5.4;
 - Step 6: Capture any further constraints on the KPI measurement process that need to be considered in design;
 - Step 7: (based on Step 5) design a mock-up for a survey tool for KPI measurement.
- Figure 2 shows these steps as a flow diagram.

Figure 2 Flow of method analysis

5. RESULTS

5.1. Step 1: Criteria for selection

The criteria that apply to the KPI monitoring approach are :

valid – the monitoring approach must measure the underpinning KPI;

- reliable – the monitoring approach must measure the KPI in a consistent way. For Ride2Rail this means both over time, and between demo sites;
- technical feasibility – any approach (whether sensing data, or using some form of survey) must be technically feasible within the constraints of the Ride2Rail, and wider Shift2Rail, eco-system;
- minimal implementation effort – even if technically feasible, any approach should require minimal or no unplanned technical development;
- suitable for the constraints of demo sites – following on from the point about reliability, the monitoring approach should not only be consistent across demo sites, it should also fit with the local constraints on recruitment, participant availability and time demands of demo site partners;
- minimal participant effort – additionally, the monitoring approach should be designed to minimise effort on the part of demo participants, in order to encourage their accurate reporting of usage of Ride2Rail. In particular, any survey approach should anticipate that the longer the survey, fewer complete responses are likely to be submitted (Hoerger, 2010).

5.2. Step 2: Monitoring options

Initially, three different approaches were considered for measurement. These were:

- *Sensed and tracked data*: using trip and user data (Murakami and Wagner, 1999) within the Ride2Rail and wider Shift2Rail ecosystem;
- *Micro survey*: Using micro surveys, either at the end of each trip or at the end of the day (as a diary) to capture near real-time data from users about their trip (Cranwell et al., 2015);
- *Summative survey*: Surveys sets at the end of the demo period requesting information around number of trips or trip experiences (Stopher, 2009).

Table 2 Benefits and drawbacks of measurement approaches presents some of the benefits and drawbacks of the sensed and tracked data, and summative survey, approaches.

After initial discussion with WP3, it was identified that there was no current feasible way to integrate an end of trip a micro survey within the Ride2Rail / Shift2Rail ecosystem. Sending separate daily survey to participants in a consistent manner, facilitated equally by the demo site partners, was not considered feasible. Therefore, the micro survey option was ruled out at an early stage.

Sensed and tracked data, and end of demo survey, was taken forward as options for more detailed consideration.

Table 2 Benefits and drawbacks of measurement approaches

	Benefits	Drawbacks
Sensed and tracked data	Little involvement of participants; no involvement of demo sites; accurate data (if available); no concerns around participants forgetting / dropping out	Requires technical development; not all data is under direct control / access of Ride2Rail (eg under control of TSPs or CFM); can be difficult to interpret / very high volumes of irrelevant data - high analysis time
Microsurvey	Can ask targeted question at time of trip; minimal forgetting; specific data for each trip	Not feasible to implement within the Shift2Rail Travel Companion, so not appropriate for passenger journeys. While technically feasible to include in the driver companion, the app does not know when the journey is completed, and therefore difficult to send at appropriate time.
Summative survey	Can ask targeted questions; can link questions to other types of question / data (e.g.	Potential for participant dropout or inaccurate data; requires demo site partners to send links to

	demographics); low effort to implement (with pre-existing online survey tools) and facilitate analysis.	demo participants (take time, room for error)
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5.3. Step 3: First review table

In order to determine the best strategy for measurement, a table was drafted (in excel) listing:

Each KPI title (from D4.2);

KPI Description (from D4.2);

Ride2Rail Ecosystem Outputs - proposed data that would be needed to accurately assess the KPI;

'Nice to have' - additional information that would improve the quality of monitoring;

Questions / comments - open questions or observations on that particular KPI.

The first draft of this table was distributed to partners in Task 5.1, as well as WP3 leads for technical review and input. This rapidly identified the potential need to capture some forms of data via some kind of online survey, and therefore an additional column was added to list the data for each KPI that might need to be elicited directly from users because of the complexities of sensing the data in the Ride2Rail, or wider, ecosystem.

5.4. Step 4: Specific measures (final table)

The table went through a number of discussions, including a group call between WP3, WP4 and WP5, as well as being presented in the meeting with CFM partners.

Several observations came to light which have influenced the choice of KPI measurement.

- Basic trip data can be linked to an anonymous, but persistent, user ID (eg it is possible to identify all trips requested by user XYZ, where XYZ is an anonymous ID).
- It is not possible to check if a trip has been completed. While trip requests and matches are captured in the data ecosystem, it is not possible to check if the trip has actually been taken or completed. This can only be confirmed by asking the users, therefore a survey approach is the only viable means for confirming trip completion.
- Trips involving multimodal journey - sensing for trips involving a secondary TSP (e.g. where a shared journey connects with a tram or rail) are particularly challenging as there is no mechanism of accessing the data of the secondary TSP trip, therefore a survey approach is the only viable means for confirming trip completion.

- GDPR – passing personal user data (e.g. email) from the CFM is very problematic because of data protection constraints.
- Several KPIs need the same data – e.g. data on origin and destination. Therefore there is quite a limited set of data required for effective monitoring.
- Rather than accessing the app through a ‘store’, the enhanced Travel Companion that includes Ride2Rail modules and the Driver Companion will be downloaded directly onto Android-only devices, through a link sent to participants. The advantage of this approach for KPI monitoring is that all participant emails will be known by demo site leaders. Therefore a survey link can be sent to participants. NB the responses to those surveys can be still anonymous, meaning that the partners who analyse the data do not have access to personal information, thus complying with GDPR and D1.3. Using the Ride2Rail service requires installation of both the Shift2Rail Travel companion and the Ride2Rail driver companion apps. Installation data will be available for both of these functionalities.
- There is no, single ‘Ride2Rail App’. Instead, this can be viewed as the Ride2Rail ‘service’. Monitoring does not need to be reported in real time – data dumps in .csv or JSON format are acceptable. These can be provided at the end of the demo period. It is assumed that local KPIs (for Athens and Brno) are recorded directly by the demonstration partners.

Based on discussion and analysis, a harmonised table was generated. Table 3 presents a harmonised version of the final table after all consultation.

Table 3 Harmonisation of feedback on measurement

KPI	Summary of assessment	Data collection
KPI#1 Number of Ride2Rail app users	During shopping process, R2R components potentially have access to request, which can be identified by anonymous user ID. Must be at least able to identify which demo site request originated from.	Can collect via Ride2Rail enhancing the Travel Companion, but can also confirm with survey.
KPI#2 Number of completed Ride2Rail app trips	Not possible to verify a trip has been completed in an easy and low effort way.	With Travel Companion data it is possible to know how many mobility requests have found a response. However we do not have the confirmation that the trip has really been carried/taken Confirmed trips must be captured with survey.
KPI#3 Number of completed multi-occupancy vehicle trips with R2R app	As with KPI#1 - can capture that shared trip was requested. However, cannot confirm that trip took place.	Driver companion can identify number of requested trips as ride share and number of passenger in each trip. Must use survey to confirm a completed trip took place.
KPI#4 Number of completed trips involving public transit/rail with R2R app	Not possible to extract data from Shift2Rail from other TSPs that trip was made. Also, may be that participant does not request multi-modal trip in service (e.g. gets shared trip to bus stop, but then buys ticket on bus). Not easy to handle pre-payment.	Must use survey to confirm completed trip took place.
KPI#5 Number of completed commuter trips with R2R app	Potential to use time and date data to identify repeated requests from the same user. However, cannot confirm trip was completed.	With Travel Companion data it is possible to know how many mobility requests have found a response. However we do not have the confirmation that the trip has really been carried/taken Confirmed

		trips must be captured with survey.
KPI#6 Number of completed rural trips with R2R app	Travel companion may have information in the cloud wallet that gives trip origin-destination. Also, for some locations (eg Athens) <i>all</i> trips are expected to be rural.	Can also ask through survey.
KPI#7 Number of Ride2Rail app downloads	Can be counted as number of downloads from any link / page that serves the apps.	Not necessary to use survey with non-demo participants.

5.5. Step 5: Simplified approach

One of the observations on the final table was that it covered different types of data in different ways for different KPIs. This breaches the constraint of making the KPIs easy to analyses, as different methods would be used for different KPIs. Therefore the KPI approach was streamlined as follows:

- KPIs 1-6 will be recorded through the survey – this gives a single approach, and minimises the need for technical development.
- There is a risk that participant recall of specific events may be poor using the survey on its own. Therefore, where technically feasible, data will also be collected from the Ride2Rail ecosystem. This includes
 - Time and date of request
 - Anonymised user ID (for passengers of rideshare, and for driver)
 - Origin and destination of request
- KPI 7 is (theoretically) non-dependent on any particular demo site. In practice, this KPI originates from before the decision to require users to manually install an app – in other words this KPI was originally to measure the number of users accessing Ride2Rail via the Android app store. In practice, this will not occur during the Ride2Rail demo period.

5.6. Step 6: Further considerations

Demo sites will be given a link to distribute to their participants. Ideally, there will be four versions of the survey – each translated into the local language.

The survey should implemented in Online Surveys (<https://www.onlinesurveys.ac.uk/>). This is an Online Survey tool suitable for research. It is GDPR compliant, and supports logic and export in a number of formats. UNEW has a license and is able to develop and distribute surveys for use in the demo phase.

It may be possible to infer whether a trip is multi-modal or rural / peri-urban from origin destination data depending on the fidelity and granularity of the positioning data. Input may be required from demo sites to interpret this data – for example to understand whether a particular location is also in a rural location.

Table 4 presents the planned approach against the criteria presented in Section 5.1, where ‘high’ (green) represents excellent compliance with the criterion, ‘medium’ (Amber) represents good compliance but with limitations, ‘poor’ (red) represents little or no compliance with the criterion.

Table 4 Criteria assessment

Criteria	Assessment
Valid - the measurement approach must measure the underpinning KPI.	Validity is high - KPIs can be measured in a meaningful way. Sensed data on its own would not cover the KPIs, but the use of the survey helps to measure the appropriate KPI construct.
Reliable - the measure must consistently measure the KPI. For Ride2Rail this means both over time, and between demo sites.	Reliability is medium - Use of the survey approach means it cannot be assumed that all participants will respond accurately. Making sure the survey is short, and that participants will not be given incentives until after completion will mitigate this. Use of sensed data from the Ride2Rail ecosystem also helps to validate survey data.
Technical feasibility - any approach (whether sensing data, or using some form of survey) must be technically feasible within the constraints of the Ride2Rail, and wider Shift2Rail, ecosystem.	Technical feasibility is high - Limited use of sensitive data and only with agreement of technical partners. Monitoring approach only focusses on those types of data under control of Ride2Rail wherever possible.
Minimal implementation effort - even if technically feasible, any approach should require minimal or no unplanned technical development.	Minimal implementation effort is high - survey will use a different tool (Online Surveys) and all other sensed data is available in Ride2Rail ecosystem.
Suitable for the constraints of demo sites - following on from the point about reliability, the measurement approach should not only be consistent	Suitability for demo sites is high - Survey will be provided through a single URL. Demo sites do not need to share emails with UNEW as survey provider.

<p>across demo sites, it should also fit with the local constraints on recruitment, participant availability and time demands of demo site partners.</p>	<p>Demo sites do not need to distribute micro surveys. May need some minimal geographic data to understand rural / peri-urban locations</p>
<p>Minimal participant effort - additionally, the methodology should be designed to minimise effort on the part of demo participants, in order to encourage their accurate reporting of usage of Ride2Rail. In particular, any survey approach should anticipate that the longer the survey, fewer complete responses are likely to be submitted (Hoerger, 2010).</p>	<p>Minimal participant effort is medium - Survey does require some input from participants but streamlined nature of KPIs means number of questions requiring input is low. Survey is anticipated to take around 5 minutes (even with usability element). Other data is sensed directly without input from users.</p>

5.7. Step 7: Survey mockup

In order to assess the feasibility of designing a short, relevant survey for use in Ride2Rail monitoring, a draft survey was developed using Online surveys. This included KPI questions, a short usability section relevant to T5.2 (see D5.2) and a short number of demographic questions.

The intention has been to keep the survey as short as possible, in order to ensure participant compliance.

Currently the survey mockup is 5 pages:

- Page 1 – Introduction and consent
- Page 2 – Demo selection
- Page 3 - KPI questions
- Page 4 – Usability questions
- Page 5 – Demographics

In practice the demo selection page (2) may be dropped and, instead, four different versions will be developed with separate links for each of the four demo sites.

Example pages are shown in the appendix. Please note, terms such as Ride2Rail app, or use of R2R will be replaced for the production version of the survey.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable has described the process and outcomes of determining the evaluation methodology for Ride2Rail, based on the KPIs described in D4.2. Having considered the scope, technical constraints and requirements of demo sites, this work has confirmed the following approach:

- KPIs 1-6 will be recorded through the survey – this gives a single approach, and minimises the need for technical development.
- Where data is available in the Ride2Rail ecosystem (e.g. count of users that have requested at least one trip [KPI#1]) this will be used to give additional validation of the recorded KPIs. KPI 7 is (theoretically) non-dependent on any particular demo site. In practice, this KPI originates from before the decision to require users to manually install an app – in other words this KPI was originally to measure the number of users accessing Ride2Rail via the Android store. In practice, this will not occur during the Ride2Rail demo period.

Outstanding issues to be resolved during the execution of Task 5.3 include:

- Determining the appropriate way to deliver survey link and who is responsible for delivering the link / page with installation link.
- Developing the full survey, and potentially integrating the usability survey (see D5.2); creating four versions each with appropriate translation.
- Understanding exactly the origin-destination data quality in order to understand opportunities for sensed analysis for multi-modal or rural/ peri-urban trips.
- Updating any KPI or monitoring requirements based on changes to the technical delivery of Ride2Rail or execution of the demonstrations
- Finally, Task 5.3 will seek to work closely with demo sites to capture their requirements (e.g. survey translation; incentivisation) for ensuring the best possible response rate to the survey from demo participants.

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APPENDIX

R2R_kpi_survey_draft (copy)

0% complete

Page 1: Introduction page

This page will introduce the survey. It may cover any GDPR type information. Etc etc.

Also might talk about the scope - are we just looking at the app or the whole Ride2Rail experience?

Indicate how long it will take - approximately 5 minutes.

Next >

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R2R_kpi_survey_draft (copy)

20% complete

Page 2: Location

Where did you participate in the Ride2Rail demo?

- Brno
- Padua
- Athens
- Helsinki
- Other

[I have not added yet, but we could have a branch for Helsinki that asks questions in the next page that are more relevant to the Robobus service]

< Previous

Next >

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R2R_kpi_survey_draft (copy)

40% complete

Page 3: R2R usage page

How many times have you used the Ride2Rail app as a **passenger** of a shared trip?

How many times have you used the Ride2Rail app as a **driver** of a shared trip?

For all of your Ride2Rail journeys, how many connected to public transit (bus, tram, train, metro) either at the beginning or the end of the trip?

For all of your Ride2Rail journeys, how many were a commute FROM home TO work / education etc?

For all of your Ride2Rail journeys, how many were a commute FROM work / education etc TO home?

For all of your Ride2Rail journeys, how many either started or ended at a rural or suburban location?

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This part of the survey uses a table of questions, [view as separate questions instead?](#)

How would you rate the Ride2Rail app on the following points? By service we mean all the elements of the service - the e-scooter itself, the app, payment, picking up or dropping off the e-scooter, using a helmet etc.

Please don't select more than 1 answer(s) per row.

	Strongly agree	Slightly agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Slightly disagree	Strongly disagree
I think that I would like to use the Ride2Rail app frequently.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I found the Ride2Rail app unnecessarily complex.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I thought the Ride2Rail app was easy to use.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use the Ride2Rail app.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I found the various functions in the Ride2Rail app were well integrated.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I thought there was too much inconsistency in this Ride2Rail app.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I would imagine that most people would learn to use the Ride2Rail app very quickly.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I found the Ride2Rail app very cumbersome to use.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I felt very confident using the Ride2Rail app.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with the Ride2Rail app.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

What is the best thing about the Ride2Rail app? What did you like about it?

What problems did you face with the Ride2Rail app? What did you dislike about it?

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80% complete

Page 5: About you

How old are you?

- 16 -21
- 22 - 35
- 36 - 51
- 52 - 65
- 65+

What do you do?

- Student
- In work
- Unemployed
- Retired
- Other

What gender do you identify as?

- Female
- Male
- Other
- Prefer not to say

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Finish ✓

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